

7th international Med-CORDEX Workshop, On line, May 2023 AGENDA

Monday 15th & Tuesday 16th, May 2023

Version: 16 May 2023

WORKSHOP OBJECTIVES:

- have scientific talks and exchanges to raise momentum in the community
- refine the CORDEX-CMIP6 Baseline run protocol
- prepare the CORDEX ICRC conference in Trieste
- start to identify new possible activities within Med-CORDEX
- introduce the new ocean biogeochemistry and coastal risk communities

WORKSHOP ORGANIZERS:

Erika Coppola, Samuel Somot, Bodo Ahrens, Gabriel Jordà, Fabien Solmon, Gianmaria Sannino, Marco Reale, Rosh Ranasinghe, Florence Sevault, Pierre Nabat, Emanuela Pichelli

REGISTRATION:

- Use the registration form <https://forms.gle/9PSSuDhxLke21HPo6> to register.
- Oral scientific contributions (Title/mini-abstract) should be directly submitted to the session chairs (see below)

TECHNICAL ASPECTS:

- Zoom link will be shared to the registered persons
- The session chairs will manage the session introduction, the oral timing, the questions or discussions and the closing session reporting
- Comments and additional questions will be possible through a dedicated open google document:

https://docs.google.com/document/d/1uDovEsVj7_wpXYKlzOxsmfL2-CoZKfbt_xg8vZRIzyMU/edit

USEFUL LINKS

- [Med-CORDEX community zenodo](#) with key documents
- [Med-CORDEX phase 3](#)
- [Med-CORDEX-CMIP6 baseline run protocol](#)
- [Med-CORDEX web](#)
- Med-CORDEX slack: <https://medcordex.slack.com> (ask to be added)
- Med-CORDEX Steering Committee contact: medcordex-sc@meteo.fr
- General Med-CORDEX emailing list: medcordex@meteo.fr

AGENDA - Monday 15th May, Morning

Introduction session [Chair: Erika Coppola, Bodo Ahrens]

- 9.30-9.50: *Welcome coffee, connection to zoom*
- 9.50-10.10: Gabriel Jordà (IEO) on behalf of the Med-CORDEX Steering Committee: *Introduction to the Med-CORDEX workshop*
- 10.10-10.25: Alessandro Anav & Marco Chericoni (ENEA/IUUS) *Dynamical downscaling of MPI-ESM1-2-HR with the ENEA-REG regional Earth system model over the Med-CORDEX region*

New CMIP6-CORDEX baseline runs session [Chair: Erika Coppola, Bodo Ahrens]

- 10.25-10.40: Francesco Maicu et al. (CMCC) *SEAS: a step forward a regional ocean-atmosphere coupled forecasting system for the Southern European Seas*
- 10.40-10.55: Florence Sevault (CNRM) *Mechanisms of heat storage and trend in the Mediterranean Sea in a high emission CMIP6 scenario with the regional climate system model CNRM-RCSM6.*

Break: 10.55 - 11.15

- 11.15-11.25: Gabriel Jordà (IEO) *Rendering of the protocol task team on model spin-up*
- 11.25-11.35: Gianmaria Sannino (ENEA) *Rendering of the protocol task team on sea level representation*
- 11.35-11.45: Samuel Somot (CNRM) *Rendering of the protocol task team on driving GCM selection*
- 11.45-12.00: Andressa Andrade Cardoso (University of São Paulo), Erika Coppola (ICTP), Julia Mindlin (Universidad de Buenos Aires) and Theodore G. Shepherd (U. Reading). *A storyline approach to select the CMIP6 model ensemble to be downscaled for the South America domain*
- 12.00-12.15: Marco Reale (OGS) & Graziano Giuliani (ICTP), *A new version of the Mediterranean RegCM-ES configuration: preliminary results and ongoing spin-up procedure*
- 12.15-12.30: Sofia Darmaraki (FORTH) *On the mixed layer heat budget behind marine heatwaves in the Mediterranean Sea*

AGENDA - Monday 15th May, Afternoon

New CMIP6-CORDEX baseline runs session (going-on) [Chair: Erika Coppola, Bodo Ahrens]

- 2.00-2.20: Daniela Jacob (GERICS) *Coming challenges, place of Med-CORDEX in CORDEX, new FPS application and preview of the ICRC conference*
- 2.20-2.35: Samuel Somot (CNRM) *Summary of the new CMIP6 baseline runs activity*
- 2.35-3.00: *Discussions on the new CMIP6 baseline runs* [Chair: Marco Reale (OGS), Florence Sevault (CNRM)]

Completed FPS activities session [Chair: Gianmaria Sannino, Emanuela Pichelli, Pierre Nabat]

- 3.00-3.15: Erika Coppola (ICTP) *Summary and lessons learned from the FPS-convection*
- 3.15-3.25: Cécile Caillaud (CNRM) *Mediterranean HPEs in a warmer climate as seen by a large convection-permitting model ensemble*

Break: 3.25 - 3.45

- 3.45-4.00: Fabien Solmon (LAERO) *Summary and lessons learned from the FPS-aerosol*
- 4.00-4.10: Vassilis Pavlidis (AUTH) *Using WRF model to investigate aerosol impacts on regional climate over Europe*
- 4.10-4.20: Gabriel Jordà (IEO) *Summary and lessons learned from the FPS-airsea*
- 4.20-4.30: Javier Soto-Navarro (U. Malaga) *Impacts of HR and air-sea coupling in future regional climate projections*
- 4.30-4.40: Camilo Melo (UCM) *On the role of mesoscale structures on air-sea coupling*
- 4.40-5.30: *Discussion on the FPS in particular on lessons learned and recommendations for submitting new FPS* [Chair: Gianmaria Sannino, Emanuela Pichelli, Pierre Nabat]

AGENDA - Tuesday 16th May, Morning

- 9.30-9.45: *Welcome coffee / recap from day 1 by session chairs*

Coastal risk session [Chair: Rosh Ranasinghe, Erika Coppola]

- 9.45-9.50 : Rosh Ranasinghe (IHE Delft/Deltares) *Introduction to the session*
- 9.50-10.05: Michalis Voudoukas (JRC) *Towards large scale assessments of coastal risks in view of climate change*
- 10.05-10.20: Khin Nawarat (IHE Delft) *Coastal hardening and potential total beach loss at global scale*
- 10.20-10.35: Francesco Dottori (CIMA Foundation) *Methods for large-scale mapping of river flood hazard*
- 10.35-11.10: *Discussions* [Chair: Rosh Ranasinghe+ Erika Coppola]

Break 11.10 - 11.30

Session on new proposed activities [Chair: Samuel Somot, Bodo Ahrens]

- 11.30-11.40: Elena Xoplaki (U. Giessen) *Mediterranean paleoclimate: simulations of the past centuries to past millennia*
- 11.40-11.50: Rihem Jabnoun (INSTM), Ali Harzallah (INSTM) *A Mediterranean Sea model forced by a set of atmospheric and oceanic forcing fields during the period 1950-2100*
- 11.50-12.30: *Discussion on possible new coordinated activities in Med-CORDEX, including at least paleoclimate modelling, ocean stand-alone modelling and storyline approach* [Chair: S. Somot, B. Ahrens]

AGENDA - Tuesday 16th May, Afternoon

Ocean biogeochemistry session [Chair: Marco Reale, Gabriel Jordà, Fabien Solmon]

- 2.00-2.05: Marco Reale (OGS) *Introduction to the session*
- 2.05-2.20: Melika Baklouti (MIO, Université d'Aix-Marseille) *Some past and potentially future characteristics of the Mediterranean Sea studied with the NEMO-MED12/Eco3M-Med model*
- 2.20-2.35: Jean-Claude Dutay (LSCE) *Neodymium budget in the Mediterranean Sea: evaluating the role of atmospheric dusts using a high-resolution dynamical-biogeochemical model*
- 2.35-2.50: Marco Reale (OGS) *Eddy resolving projections for the biogeochemistry of the Mediterranean Sea under two different emission scenarios: main important outcomes and possible applications*
- 2.50-3.05: Ginevra Rosati (OGS) *Biogeochemical and physical drivers of MeHg dynamics in the Mediterranean Sea: insights from a coupled 3D model*
- 3.05-3.30: *Discussions* [Chair: Marco Reale, Gabriel Jordà, Fabien Solmon]

Break: 3.30 - 3.50

Closing session [Chair: Bodo Ahrens, Samuel Somot]

- 3.50-4.10: *Discussions on the new CMIP6 baseline runs (part 2)* [Chair: Marco Reale (OGS), Florence Sevault (CNRM)]
- 4.10-4.40: *Report of the sessions by the chairs (5 minutes/session) take home messages and list of actions*
- 4.40-5.00: *Final discussions* [Chair: Bodo Ahrens, Samuel Somot]

PARTICIPANT LIST (106)

Samuel	Somot	Météo-France/CNRM
Bodo	Ahrens	Goethe University Frankfurt
Gianmaria	Sannino	ENEA
Erika	Coppola	ICTP
Jessica	Castagna	University of Calabria
Christos	Giannakopoulos	National Observatory of Athens
Yoav	Levi	Israel Meteorological Service
Virginia Edith	Cortes Hernandez	CNRM-Meteo-France
Pavel	Khain	Israel Meteorological Service
Melika	Baklouti	Mediterranean Institute of Oceanography
Konstantinos V.	Varotsos	National Observatory of Athens
Stefano	Salon	OGS
Camilo	Melo-Aguilar	Universidad Complutense de Madrid
Eduardo	Ramirez-Romero	Instituto Ciencias Marinas de Andalucia ICMAN-CSIC, Spain
Myrto	Gratsea	National Observatory of Athens
William	Cabos	Universidad de Alcala
Florence	Sevault	Météo-France
Caroline	Ulses	LEGOS
Marco	Reale	National Institute of Oceanography and Applied Geophysics-OGS
Ali	Harzallah	INSTM
Cécile	Caillaud	CNRM
Pierre	Nabat	Météo-France / CNRM
Laurent	Li	LMD/IPSL, CNRS, Sorbonne Université
Margot	Bador	CECI CNRS-Cerfacs
Diego	Macias	European Commission, Joint Research Centre
Dutay	Jean-Claude	LSCE
Leenes	Uzan	Israel Meteorological Service (IMS)

Yoav	Levi	Israel Met. Service (IMS)
Alba	De La Vara	Kveloce I+D+i (Senior Europa S.L.)
Roshanka	Ranasinghe	IHE Delft
Khin	Nawarat	IHE Delft Institute for Water Education
Trang	Duong	IHE Delft/University of Twente, The Netherlands
Javier	Soto-Navarro	GOFIMA - University of Málaga
Neelam	Rajput	Goethe University Frankfurt
Marco	Chericoni	IUSS Pavia and ENEA
Alessandro	Anav	ENEA
Alessandro	Dell'Aquila	ENEA
Ted	Shepherd	University of Reading
Jullia	Mindlin	Universidad de Buenos Aires
Andressa	Andrade Cardoso	University of São Paulo
Sandro	Calmanti	ENEA
Marta	Antonelli	ENEA
Maria Vittoria	Struglia	ENEA
Ernesto	Napolitano	ENEA
Vincent	Guarinos	Aix-Marseille Université
Joan	Villalonga	Universitat de les Illes Balears
Gabriel	Jorda	Spanish Institute of Oceanography
Jakob	Haltmeyer	FH IMC Krems
Elena	Xoplaki	Justus Liebig University Giessen
Mohamed	Ayache	LSCE
Marco	Fianchini	OGS
Francesco	Dattilo	OGS
Corre	Lola	Météo-France
Donata	Canu	OGS
Ginevra	Rosati	National Institute of Oceanography and Applied Geophysics - OGS
Isabella	Scroccaro	OGS
Bastin	Sophie	LATMOS/IPSL
Romain	Pennel	LMD/IPSL
Neelam	Rajput	Goethe University
Rita M	Cardoso	Universidade de Lisboa, Instituto Dom Luiz

Silvio	Gualdi	Centro Euro-Mediterraneo sui Cambiamenti Climatici
Rihem	Jabnoun	INSTM
Vasileios	Pavlidis	ARISTOTLE UNIVERSITY OF THESSALONIKI
Sofia	Darmaraki	FORTH
Jessica	Castagna	University of Calabria
Laura	Feudale	OGS
Meier	Markus	Leibniz Institute for Baltic Sea Research Warnemünde
Vladimir	Djurdjevic	Faculty of Physics, University of Belgrade
Ibrahim	Ben Aziz	Ministère Des Transports
Iván	Parras Berrocal	University of Cádiz
Gonzalez	Nicolas	CNRM
José C.	Sánchez-Garrido	University of Málaga
Stergios	Kartsios	Aristotle University of Thessaloniki
Bernard	Niyigena	University of Rwanda
Francesco	Dottori	CIMA Research Foundation
Kyaw	Than Oo	Nanjing University of Information Science and Technology
Paolo	Lazzari	Istituto Nazionale di Oceanografia e di Geofisica Sperimentale
Simona	Masina	CMCC
Polcher	Jan	LMD-IPSL
John	Karagiorgos	National and Kapodistrian University of Athens/Ocean Physics and Modelling Group
Michalis	Vousdoukas	University of the Aegean
Francesco	Maicu	CMCC
Adriana	Carillo	ENEA
Eleni	Katragkou	Aristotle University of Thessaloniki
Dmitry	Sein	AWI
Ségolène	Berthou	UK Met Office
Konstantinos	Varotsos	National Observatory of Athens
Doury	Antoine	CNRS-CNRM
Barış	Önol	Istanbul Technical University
Mallet	Marc	CNRM
Claude	Estournel	CNRS

Emanuela	Pichelli	ICTP
Luca	Furnari	University of Calabria
Giorgia	Verri	CMCC
Riccardo	Martellucci	OGS
Renata	Tatsch Eidt	University of Bologna
Vladimir	Santos Da Costa	CMCC
Fabio	Viola	CMCC
Tomas	Halenka	Charles University
Robin	Waldman	CNRM
Graziano	Giuliani	ICTP
Murat	Gunduz	DEU-IMST, CMCC
Mingyue	Zhang	Justus Liebig University of Giessen
Maria Vittoria	Guarino	ICTP
Jesus	Fernandez	Instituto de Física de Cantabria (IFCA), CSIC-Universidad de Cantabria, Santander, Spain
Fabien	Solmon	LAERO /CNRS / Université de Toulouse
Marta	Alvarez	IEO-CSIC